

Psychological Factors of (Un)Conventional Online Political Activity Acceptability among Russian Youth

Ekaterina V. Maklasova¹

¹ HSE University, Moscow, 101000, Russia

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Abstract

Russian youth represent a significant part of the population, playing a key role in the development of society and possessing high innovative potential. In the context of digitalization, young people, as the main users of digital technologies, have acquired new resources for the formation of political views and civic positions, as well as opportunities for active participation in the socio-political life of the country. However, this process has also increased the vulnerability of the younger generation to the influence of opposition political forces, which recognize its importance and use digital technologies for ideological impact.

At the same time, a generalized approach to the study of political activity that ignores modern socio-political and technological changes highlights the need for a more in-depth analysis of the factors determining young people's political engagement. To date, the role of social capital in the political activity of young people in the digital space remains insufficiently studied, despite its obvious importance.

Therefore, this study aims to examine the role of digital literacy in the relationship between social capital and the acceptability of (un)conventional online political activity among Russian youth aged 15 to 25 years. The results of a mediation analysis conducted using structural equation modeling showed that social capital was positively associated with the acceptability of both forms of online political activity, while digital literacy was positively associated with conventional online political activity and negatively associated with unconventional online political activity. Moreover, digital literacy mediated the relationship between social capital and conventional online political activity positively, and with unconventional online political activity negatively.

Thus, the study revealed the significant role of social capital and digital literacy in shaping the acceptability of various forms of online political activity among young people, emphasizing their importance for further research in the context of digitalization.

Keywords

youth, political activity, social capital, digital literacy, digitalization, mediation models

JEL codes: Y80, Z18, Z19

Introduction

Russian youth constitute a significant part of the country's population, playing a key role in social development and possessing considerable innovative potential. Their active participation in social and political life influences the development of civil society, the formation of political culture, and the socio-economic progress of the state.

For a long time, the problem of low socio-political activity among young people has remained relevant (Bashurina 2021). This issue has negatively affected the development of their civic position, provoked social contradictions and conflicts, and hindered the growth of democratic institutions in the country (Vinokurov 2022).

With the advent of digitalization, young people – as the primary users of digital technologies – have acquired new resources for shaping political views and civic positions, as well as new opportunities for socio-political participation. Thus, digitalization is becoming one of the factors that increase the political activity of Russian youth (Vasileva et al. 2021).

However, scholars also note (Stanevich 2018; Vasileva et al. 2021) that digitalization has made the younger generation more vulnerable to the ideological influence of opposition political forces, which encourage unconventional political activity. Such activity can destabilize the socio-political situation in the country and hinder the sustainable development of society.

In this context, the study of factors determining the acceptability of (un)conventional forms of online political activity among young people is becoming increasingly urgent.

Political activity may be defined as “the activity of citizens, carried out both individually (e.g., party or electoral activity) and collectively – indirectly through political parties, movements, or organizations (e.g., filing petitions, demonstrations, and protests) – in various (un)conventional forms, with the aim of influencing the political system of the country” (Chirun 2010; Bashurina 2021). At the same time, different views exist regarding the distinction between individual and collective activity. For instance, Chirun (2010) and Bashurina (2021) argue that individual activity may include party and electoral activity, while collective activity may involve efforts aimed at solving specific problems, expressed, for example, through the filing of petitions.

Political activity is generally understood to manifest itself at both behavioural and attitudinal levels. The behavioural level refers to the active participation of citizens in the socio-political life of the country, including such actions as voting in elections, working in government bodies, joining political parties and movements, and engaging in the activities of public organizations. The attitudinal level reflects citizens' attitudes toward the political situation in the country, their interest in political processes, awareness of the work of government agencies, and their stance on participation in political life (Petukhov 2000; Bashurina 2021).

Various typologies of political activity have been proposed, with the most widely used being that of L. Milbrath, who distinguishes between conventional and unconventional forms (Vinokurov 2022).

Conventional political activity typically includes membership and participation in public associations and organizations such as foundations, trade unions, political parties, voluntary societies (e.g., scientific, cultural, educational, or sports associations), mass movements, and creative unions. It also involves participation in elections at different levels, campaigning, supporting parties or candidates (including financial support), participating in referendums, various forms of interaction with government officials, involvement in legislative bodies, signing petitions, and participation in peaceful demonstrations (Pfetser 2013; Vinokurov 2022).

Unconventional political activity, by contrast, may involve boycotting elections, refusing to pay taxes, hunger strikes, signing unauthorized petitions, organizing or participating in unauthorized rallies, spontaneous strikes and riots, acts of civil disobedience, the creation of alternative power structures (e.g., “people’s councils”), or the seizure of buildings (Pfetser 2013; Vinokurov 2022).

With the advent of digitalization, traditional forms of political activity have been modified and adapted to the digital environment, while numerous new forms have also emerged (Barsegyan 2014; Bashurina 2021). Online political activity now encompasses a wide range of practices, including:

- participation in online voting and referendums;
- engagement in online surveys and research on political issues;
- interaction with other Internet users through comments, likes, reposts, and reviews on political topics;
- communication with political bloggers, activists, organizations, parties, candidates, leaders, and experts via digital platforms;
- subscription to online newsletters, channels, groups, and communities related to politics;
- creation and dissemination of political content (e.g., articles, videos, posts);
- moderation of online groups and pages dedicated to political issues;
- involvement in virtual political events such as flash mobs, festivals, demonstrations, and rallies;
- participation in online petitions, donations, and crowdfunding campaigns aimed at addressing political problems;
- engagement in online lectures, seminars, trainings, games, simulators, and courses designed to enhance political literacy and foster political culture;
- organization and participation in online discussions, webinars, debates, conferences, and forums on political issues;
- contribution to online consultations on matters of public policy.

It is evident that young people, as the most active Internet users, constitute the primary participants in online political activity (Vinokurov 2022). Whereas several decades ago scholars emphasized the low level of youth political involvement (Barsegyan 2014), today digitalization has significantly expanded young people’s opportunities for political participation, as confirmed by recent studies (Bashurina 2021; Vinokurov 2022). At the same time, youth political activity remains volatile and cyclical, often rising in response to critical national events or periods of socio-political tension (Bashurina 2021; Belikova 2014). Some of these surges have coincided with the broader digitalization of Russian society (Vinokurov 2022).

At the same time, digitalization increases the vulnerability of younger citizens to opposition political forces, which actively employ digital technologies and innovations to exert ide-

ological influence on one of the most important groups in the country's political life. Such influence is often aimed at achieving pragmatic goals, including destabilizing the socio-political situation and undermining sustainable development (Vinokurov 2022; Baranova and Novikov 2018; Ananchenko et al. 2022).

When discussing youth political activity, it is customary to define this category as citizens aged 15 to 24, since this period is marked by intensive secondary political socialization, during which individuals develop feedback mechanisms and personal political views. Within this age group, two subcategories can be distinguished based on the scope of political rights: 15–17 years and 18–24 years (Ananchenko et al. 2022).

Youth are generally characterized by a duality in their political views and positions. On the one hand, they hold democratic values and are oriented toward pro-national ideas; on the other, they demonstrate low institutional trust and a pronounced desire for absolute freedom. This ambivalence highlights the specificity of youth political activity and its difference from the political engagement of society as a whole (Vinokurov 2022).

Contemporary research shows that youth political activity is influenced by a wide range of factors. These include demographic characteristics such as geographical location (Sokolovsky and Banshchikova 2022; Beznosov and Pochebut 2023), gender and age (Zagranichnyy 2020; Arendachuk 2020; Beznosov and Pochebut 2023); cultural and social attitudes (Zaitsev 2008; Fomina et al. 2022a; Beznosov and Pochebut 2023), as well as cultural and ideological orientations (Zaitsev 2008; Ananchenko et al. 2022; Beznosov and Pochebut 2023; Fomina et al. 2022b). Individual-level determinants include values (Shamionov et al. 2022), religious affiliation and degree of religiosity (Barsukova et al. 2022), motivation (Vinokurov 2022; Beznosov and Pochebut 2023), self-regulation style (Fomina et al. 2022a), and volitional qualities (Shamionov et al. 2019). Social and institutional factors also play an important role, including social capital (Omelchenko et al. 2016; Derevyanchenko and Kalinin 2020), institutional trust (Zaitsev 2008; Kirichek 2012; Vinokurov 2022), political self-efficacy (Zaitsev 2008; Kirichek 2012; Gulevich et al. 2017; Gulevich and Guseva 2022), legal culture (Dzyaloshinskii 2009; Kirichek 2012; Bashurina 2021), the dominant form of legal consciousness (Kirichek 2012; Beznosov and Pochebut 2023), and the prevailing model of political behaviour (Ananchenko et al. 2022).

Despite the breadth of existing studies, most adopt a generalized perspective that does not always adequately reflect the fundamental distinction between conventional and unconventional forms of political activity. This limitation reduces the depth of understanding of the mechanisms and factors underlying different types of political engagement.

It should be noted that many studies on the factors of political activity were conducted one or two decades ago. Given the dynamic socio-political environment of that period – marked by profound economic, political, and socio-cultural transformations – it is reasonable to assume corresponding shifts in the psychological profile of contemporary youth. These shifts may, in turn, necessitate a reconsideration of previously established patterns and dependencies in the study of political activity.

Equally important is the pervasive digital transformation that has reshaped key domains of modern society. This process has not only redefined the essence of political activity but also significantly transformed its traditional forms. The proliferation of digital technologies has created new channels of communication, platforms for self-expression, and tools for organizing collective action. These changes have profoundly influenced modes of political participation, particularly among young people, who are the primary consumers of digital

services and technologies, as well as the processes of shaping the political agenda. Nevertheless, current research does not consistently address these dynamics, suggesting the need for further investigation and deeper analysis.

It should also be emphasized that in some studies youth are not treated as a distinct subject of political life, which represents a significant limitation. Overlooking the specific characteristics of young people – such as their unique experiences of digital socialization, value orientations that differ from those of older generations, heightened receptivity to new ideas, and active use of online platforms for political expression – results in an incomplete understanding of the dynamics of political participation. Considering the growing role of youth as a catalyst for social change, as well as their vulnerability to disinformation, recognizing them as an independent object of research appears particularly important.

At the same time, existing studies of online political activity among Russian youth often fail to adequately address the role of social capital. This omission significantly restricts the understanding of how young citizens become engaged in political processes in the digital environment. Social capital – shaped in particular through social networks and online communities – plays a crucial role in the formation of political views, the mobilization of young people, and their participation in various forms of online political activity.

Current research highlights the significant role of both bonding and bridging social capital as catalysts for the development of digital literacy. They do so by facilitating access to resources, stimulating knowledge exchange, fostering trust in technology, and supporting the adoption of new practices. Bridging social capital, in particular, has been shown to negatively correlate with distrust of digital technologies – an issue that posed a major barrier to digitalization only a few years ago. Through their social networks, individuals receive positive examples of technology use, which reduces fear of adoption and contributes to the acquisition of digital skills (Borodkina and Sibirev 2021; Vartanova and Gladkova 2020).

Bonding social capital, expressed through close social networks and ties, enhances access to diverse digital information sources, encourages the exchange of knowledge and experience, and strengthens communication in the digital environment. This process involves not only the acquisition of basic Internet skills but also the development of more complex competencies, such as digital critical thinking. For example, participation in virtual teams and professional communities enables individuals to share expert solutions and adopt new practices, thereby directly increasing their digital literacy (Guzhavina 2021).

Furthermore, individuals with higher levels of bridging social capital are more likely to receive recommendations, training, and support from their social contacts, which facilitates the mastering of digital technologies (Zhukovskaya 2020). Studies also show a positive relationship between bonding social capital and involvement in innovative digital practices: social connections provide motivation and support that promote adaptation to new technologies (Zhukovskaya 2020; Guzhavina 2021).

Over the past decade, political activism has become an integral part of digital practices. With the advance of digitalization, many traditional forms of political participation have been transformed and adapted to the conditions of the digital society, while entirely new forms of engagement have also emerged (Barsegyan 2014; Bashurina 2021).

Within the sphere of online political activity, bridging social capital enables users to more easily find like-minded individuals and organize collective actions, such as participating

in protests or supporting specific political initiatives (Belyaeva 2019). Bonding social capital, in turn, facilitates the creation and maintenance of virtual communities that function as platforms for information dissemination and opinion exchange (Derevyanchenko and Kalinin 2020). These communities enhance citizens' political awareness and interest, allow for quicker responses to political events, and foster deeper involvement in political life (Chebunina 2019; Derevyanchenko and Kalinin 2020; Bushkova-Shiklina and Kushova 2022).

Moreover, bonding social capital in virtual environments promotes broader participation across diverse segments of the population. By overcoming geographical, age, and social barriers, it contributes to the formation of a more inclusive civil society (Belyaeva 2019; Bushkova-Shiklina and Kushova 2022).

Numerous studies highlight a positive relationship between digital literacy and online political activity. High levels of digital literacy are associated with greater engagement in public debates (Shikhgafizov et al. 2023) and political discussions (Sharkov et al. 2020); participation in online protests (Sharkov et al. 2020; Abdulyakeen and Yusuf 2022; Tamang et al. 2025); and involvement in online surveys, signature campaigns, and forum discussions (Abdulyakeen and Yusuf 2022). Individuals with strong digital skills are more likely to use digital technologies to access and disseminate information on socio-political issues, elections, and civil initiatives (Sharkov et al. 2020); to express opinions (Shikhgafizov et al. 2023); and to organize or take part in protest events (Lebedeva and Minaeva 2023; Tamang et al. 2025).

At the same time, some studies point to the nuanced role of digital literacy in shaping preferences for conventional versus unconventional forms of political participation in the digital environment. For instance, Derevyanchenko and Kalinin (2020) found that digitally literate youth tend to favor socially acceptable and formalized modes of political engagement. Similarly, Gerasimova et al. (2024) observed that individuals with high digital skills prefer activities that allow them to maintain control over information and apply critical analysis. In a more cautious interpretation, Pyрма (2019) argued that digitally literate individuals, aware of the risks inherent in online environments, tend to prefer conventional forms of participation to avoid potential negative consequences associated with digital activism.

In light of the above, the following research questions guide this study:

1. How are bonding and bridging social capital related to the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity among Russian youth aged 15–25?
2. What role does digital literacy play in the relationship between bonding and bridging social capital and the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity among Russian youth aged 15–25?

Methods and Design

This study employs a cross-sectional correlational design to investigate the socio-psychological factors influencing the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity. The independent variables are bonding and bridging social capital, while digital literacy serves as a mediator. The dependent variable is the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity among Russian youth.

Sample

The study involved 390 respondents aged 15 to 25 years ($M = 20$, mode = 24, $SD = 3$), of whom 70.6% were women.

Geographical distribution: 33.8% were from the Central Federal District; 17.1% from the Northwestern; 12.3% from the Ural; 10% from the Siberian; 9.8% from the Southern; 9.7% from the Volga; 4.6% from the North Caucasian; and 2.8% from the Far Eastern Federal District.

Educational background: 31.7% had completed secondary vocational education; 24.3% higher education; 23.8% secondary general education; 16.9% basic general education; and 3.4% primary vocational education.

Income level (mode = 5): 35.5% could afford durable goods; 29.7% could afford food and clothing; 10% only food; 12.3% could not afford major purchases such as an apartment or a summer house; 9.5% could afford everything; and 4.1% could afford nothing.

Political orientation: 56.8% identified as social democrats; 10.2% liberals; 7.7% communists; 6.6% conservatives; 5.9% pacifists; 5.9% nationalists; 1.8% anarchists; 1.5% monarchists; 0.8% extremists (Nazi or fascist ideologies, banned in Russia); and 2.6% considered themselves apolitical.

Institutional trust was slightly above average ($M = 6$, $SD = 2$, min = 1, max = 10), with the most characteristic feature being absolute trust in government institutions (mode = 9.86).

Civic identity was relatively high ($M = 5$, mode = 5, $SD = 0.8$, min = 1, max = 6).

Religious affiliation and religiosity: 50.1% identified as Orthodox ($M = 6.43$, $SD = 2.13$); 12.8% as Muslim ($M = 7.48$, $SD = 2.04$); 0.8% as Jewish ($M = 7$, $SD = 2.65$); 1.3% as Catholic ($M = 6.60$, $SD = 2.41$); 1.3% as Buddhist ($M = 7.60$, $SD = 2.88$); and 33.8% reported no religious affiliation ($M = 2.77$, $SD = 1.98$). Overall religiosity was at an average level ($M = 5.35$, $SD = 2.80$, min = 1, max = 10), and religious identity was slightly above average ($M = 4.04$, mode = 5, $SD = 1.3$, min = 1, max = 6).

Procedure

A purposive sampling strategy was employed for this study. Data were collected via a socio-psychological survey administered on the online platform Anketolog.ru. Respondents received an invitation through the platform's internal messaging system, which included information about the study's initiator, objectives, confidentiality assurances, expected time to complete the survey, and details of any incentives for participation.

The survey comprised several blocks of statements designed to assess bonding and bridging social capital, digital literacy, and the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity. In addition, the questionnaire collected socio-demographic information, including district of residence, gender, age, education, income, religious affiliation and degree of religiosity, political orientation, as well as civic and religious identity.

Participation in the survey was voluntary and self-paced, with no external control over completion time. On average, respondents spent approximately 20 minutes completing the questionnaire.

Tools

Social capital was measured using the methodology developed by D. Williams (Williams 2006). This instrument assesses bonding (10 items; $\alpha = 0.798$; $D(390) = 0.0661$, $p = 0.065$; $M = 3.5$, $SD = 0.6$) and bridging (10 items; $\alpha = 0.832$; $D(390) = 0.0499$, $p = 0.283$; $M = 3.4$, $SD = 0.6$) social capital. The scale consists of 20 statements reflecting respondents' relationships with friends and acquaintances. Participants rate their agreement on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("Absolutely disagree") to 5 ("Absolutely agree"). For example: "Among my acquaintances, there are several people whom I would trust to solve my problems."

Digital literacy was assessed using the methodology proposed by Maklasova et al. (2025). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) indicated a good model fit: $CMIN/df = 2.40$, $RMSEA = 0.312$, $PCLOSE = 0.062$, $GFI = 0.995$, $AGFI = 0.986$, $CFI = 0.995$, with factor loadings ranging from 0.48 to 0.93. The instrument evaluates several skill domains relevant to the modern digital environment:

- Data analysis skills (2 items; $\alpha = 0.766$; $D(390) = 0.0408$, $p = 0.533$; $M = 2.7$, $SD = 1.4$);
- Digital skills for working with information (5 items; $\alpha = 0.737$; $D(390) = 0.0591$, $p = 0.130$; $M = 3.9$, $SD = 1.1$);
- Skills for setting up digital equipment (3 items; $\alpha = 0.746$; $D(390) = 0.0644$, $p = 0.061$; $M = 3.8$, $SD = 1.3$);
- Skills for working with software (3 items; $\alpha = 0.834$; $D(390) = 0.203$, $p = 0.622$; $M = 3.9$, $SD = 1.3$).

Respondents rated their agreement with 13 statements on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from "Not at all like me" to "Very like me." For example: "I can work with big data."

To assess *the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity*, an original methodology was developed based on domestic and international research (e.g., Bashurina 2021; Vinokurov 2022; Pfetser 2013) and tested on a sample of 200 participants aged 14–25 years ($M = 20$, $Med = 21$, $Mode = 24$, $SD = 3$). Exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses (EFA and CFA) indicated a good fit for a two-factor model explaining 52% of the variance in the studied phenomenon: $CMIN/df = 1.58$, $RMSEA = 0.05$, $PCLOSE = 0.30$, $GFI = 0.90$, $AGFI = 0.86$, $CFI = 0.96$, with factor loadings ranging from 0.53 to 0.82.

The instrument assesses the acceptability of unconventional political activity (14 items; $\alpha = 0.92$; $\omega = 0.91$; $D(390) = 0.0544$, $p = 0.197$; $M = 2.2$, $SD = 0.8$) and conventional political activity (11 items; $\alpha = 0.89$; $\omega = 0.88$; $D(390) = 0.0603$, $p = 0.116$; $M = 3.2$, $SD = 0.9$) in the digital environment. Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega values indicate high internal consistency for both scales. Respondents rate the acceptability of various forms of political participation on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "unacceptable" to "acceptable." Examples include "constructive interaction with Internet users (e.g., comments, likes, reposts, reviews) on a political topic" for conventional activity, and "Internet trolling of political bloggers, activists, organizations, parties, candidates, leaders, experts, and other figures" for unconventional activity.

Convergent validity of the instrument was supported by Pearson correlation coefficients ($r = 0.15$ – 0.37) with related constructs, including scales of online political activity (political self-expression on the Internet and political online activism) (Tatarko et al. 2024) and socio-political activity (cynicism and aggressiveness), which reflect the constructiveness of citizens' political behavior (Usova 2018).

Mathematical and statistical data processing

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 22.0 and SPSS AMOS version 20.0. Initial data processing included identifying and analyzing missing values, testing for normal distribution using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and assessing the internal consistency of the scales with Cronbach’s alpha.

To examine the relationships between social capital and the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity, as well as the mediating role of digital literacy, four mediation models were constructed. In each model:

- The independent variable was either bonding or bridging social capital.
- The mediator was a latent factor representing digital literacy, combining its component skills.
- The dependent variable was either conventional or unconventional online political activity.

These models allowed for the assessment of both direct and indirect (mediated) effects of social capital on online political activity.

Results

Figure 1 illustrates the mediation model examining the relationships between bonding social capital, digital literacy, and the acceptability of conventional online political activity. The model demonstrated a good fit to the empirical data: CMIN/df = 3.52, CFI = 0.96, RMSEA = 0.08, PCLOSE = 0.06, GFI = 0.98, AGFI = 0.94.

All direct paths in the model – between bonding social capital, digital literacy, and the acceptability of conventional online political activity – were statistically significant and positive. Furthermore, digital literacy significantly mediated the relationship between bonding social capital and the acceptability of conventional online political activity. The model accounted for 8% of the variance in the acceptability of conventional online political activity.

Figure 1. Mediation model for bonding social capital, digital literacy, and acceptability of conventional online political activity. Note: *p ≤ .05; **p ≤ .01.

Figure 2 illustrates the mediation model examining the relationships between bridging social capital, digital literacy, and the acceptability of conventional online political activity. The model showed a good fit to the empirical data: CMIN/df = 2.25, CFI = 0.98, RMSEA = 0.06, PCLOSE = 0.34, GFI = 0.99, AGFI = 0.96.

All direct paths between bridging social capital, digital literacy, and the acceptability of conventional online political activity were statistically significant and positive. Digital literacy also significantly mediated the relationship between bridging social capital and acceptability of conventional online political activity, indicating a positive mediation effect. The model explained 26% of the variance in the acceptability of conventional online political activity.

Figure 2. Mediation model for bridging social capital, digital literacy, and acceptability of conventional online political activity. *Note:* * $p \leq .05$; ** $p \leq .01$. The mediation effect is indicated by the dotted line.

Figure 3 illustrates the mediation model examining the relationships between bonding social capital, digital literacy, and the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. The model demonstrated an excellent fit to the empirical data: CMIN/df = 1.00, CFI = 1.00, RMSEA = 0, PCLOSE = 0.72, GFI = 1.00, AGFI = 0.98.

Figure 3. Mediation model for bonding social capital, digital literacy, and acceptability of unconventional online political activity. *Note:* * $p \leq .05$; ** $p \leq .01$. The mediation effect is indicated by the dotted line.

Bonding social capital was positively and significantly associated with both digital literacy and the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. In contrast, digital literacy was negatively and significantly related to the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. Furthermore, digital literacy significantly mediated the relationship between bonding social capital and the acceptability of unconventional online political activity, indicating a negative mediation effect. The model accounted for 63% of the variance in the acceptability of unconventional online political activity.

Figure 4 illustrates the mediation model examining the relationships between bridging social capital, digital literacy, and the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. The model demonstrated a good fit to the empirical data: CMIN/df = 2.88, CFI = 0.98, RMSEA = 0.07, PCLOSE = 0.19, GFI = 0.99, AGFI = 0.95.

Figure 4. Mediation model for bridging social capital, digital literacy, and acceptability of unconventional online political activity. *Note:* * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.005$. The mediation effect is indicated by the dotted line.

Bridging social capital was positively and significantly associated with both digital literacy and the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. In contrast, digital literacy was negatively and significantly related to the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. Digital literacy also significantly mediated the relationship between bridging social capital and acceptability of unconventional online political activity, indicating a negative mediation effect. The model explained 45% of the variance in the acceptability of unconventional online political activity.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to examine the mediating role of digital literacy in the relationship between social capital and the acceptability of (un)conventional online political activity among Russian youth aged 15–25. The results highlight the significant role of both social capital and digital literacy in shaping young people’s attitudes toward various forms of online political participation.

Firstly, a positive relationship was found between bonding social capital and the acceptability of both conventional and unconventional online political activity. This finding can be explained by the fact that bonding social capital – formed through close ties within

groups such as family, friends, and tight-knit communities – is associated with trust and mutual support. These networks may enhance receptivity to political participation, including online forms. For instance, discussions of political issues within these groups may stimulate interest in both conventional (e.g., online voting) and unconventional (e.g., online petitions) political activities. This conclusion aligns with previous sociological research emphasizing the role of social support networks in increasing the civic engagement of young people (Omelchenko et al. 2016).

Secondly, bridging social capital was positively associated with the acceptability of both conventional and unconventional online political activity. Bridging social capital, which connects different social groups, can broaden the social “horizons” of young people beyond their usual environments. An expanded social network provides access to diverse perspectives and information, which is particularly important for fostering an active civic position in the context of societal digitalization. Previous research indicates that Russian youth actively use social media to discuss political issues and participate in online activities (Chernov 2021; Derevyanchenko and Kalinin 2020). Thus, bridging social capital plays a significant role in engaging young people in socio-political processes.

Thirdly, digital literacy was found to play a positive mediating role in the relationship between social capital (both bonding and bridging) and the acceptability of conventional online political activity, and a negative mediating role with respect to the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. Social capital catalyzes the development of digital literacy by enabling individuals to expand their networks, exchange information, create interest groups, and participate in socio-political practices (Vartanova and Gladkova 2020; Zhukovskaya 2020; Borodkina and Sibirev 2021; Guzhavina 2021).

Through enhanced digital skills, individuals gain both a new digital space to exercise their social capital and a means to further enrich it. These skills encompass not only basic Internet competencies but also advanced abilities, such as critical thinking in digital environments. Critical thinking is crucial when choosing between conventional and unconventional online political activities, as it increases information selectivity, reduces susceptibility to viral or emotionally charged content, and enhances the ability to assess risks and consequences of participation. Consequently, it decreases the likelihood of involvement in illegal or harmful political activities online (Pyrma 2019; Derevyanchenko and Kalinin 2020; Gerasimova et al. 2024).

Overall, the results of this study underscore the importance of both social capital and digital literacy in shaping the acceptability of various forms of online political activity among Russian youth aged 15–25. The positive associations between bonding and bridging social capital and the acceptability of both conventional and unconventional online political activity suggest that strong and diverse social ties – both within close-knit groups and across broader networks – enhance young people’s receptivity to participating in the socio-political life of the country.

Given that the socialization of modern youth occurs in a digital environment, where they are primary consumers of online services, online forms of political activity are particularly accessible and appealing. At the same time, the negative mediating role of digital literacy for unconventional online political activity indicates that young people with well-developed digital skills are more selective in processing information and more critical in assessing the risks and consequences of different forms of online participation. As a result, conventional forms of online political activity emerge as the most preferable for digitally literate youth.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the cross-sectional correlational design allows only for the identification of directional relationships between the studied constructs, rather than establishing true causal effects. Future research could benefit from experimental or quasi-experimental designs, as well as longitudinal or sequential studies to assess the stability of these effects over time and across different cohorts. Additionally, cross-cultural studies may help identify generalizable trends across diverse cultural and regional contexts.

Second, the use of self-report measures introduces the risk of bias due to social desirability, subjective perception, and memory errors, which may affect the reliability of the identified relationships. Similarly, the use of a non-probability sampling strategy limits the representativeness of the data and the generalizability of the findings. Regional affiliation was also difficult to capture and control. Moreover, data collection via a voluntary online platform could have introduced self-selection bias, favoring respondents with higher digital literacy.

Finally, while the study focuses on relatively underexplored psychological constructs influencing the acceptability of (un)conventional online political activity, it does not incorporate other relevant factors identified in offline political activity research, such as institutional trust, political self-efficacy, and normative beliefs. Future studies could develop more complex predictive models that integrate these variables. External influences, including the political situation in the country, media effects, educational policies, and legislative restrictions on Internet activity, were also not considered, yet they may significantly affect young people's acceptance of different forms of political activity.

Conclusion

This study examined the mediating role of digital literacy in the relationship between social capital and the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity among Russian youth aged 15–25.

The results showed that both bonding and bridging social capital were positively associated with the acceptability of conventional and unconventional online political activity. Bonding social capital, formed through close ties within groups such as family, friends, and relatives, and bridging social capital, formed through connections across diverse social groups, appear to enhance young people's receptivity to participation in socio-political life. Given that modern youth are socialized in the digital era and are primary users of digital technologies, online forms of political activity are particularly accessible and appealing.

The study also revealed that digital literacy plays a significant mediating role. It positively mediates the relationship between social capital and the acceptability of conventional online political activity, while negatively mediating the acceptability of unconventional online political activity. Digital literacy enhances information selectivity and critical assessment of risks and consequences, which may reduce engagement in unconventional online political activity and increase preference for conventional forms. In this way, digital literacy bridges the realization of social capital in digital spaces with safer and socially accepted forms of political participation.

Overall, the study provides new insights into the formation of the civic position of modern Russian youth and highlights the potential of digital technologies as tools to foster greater engagement in conventional socio-political activities within the digital environment.

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Information about the author

- Ekaterina Vladimirovna Maklasova – Candidate of Psychology, Research Fellow at the Centre for Sociocultural Research of National Research University «Higher School of Economics». Moscow, 101000, Russia. Email: emaklasova@hse.ru